

**THE EFFECT OF FIBER ORIENTATION ON THE WEAR BEHAVIOR
OF GRAPHITE-EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIALS**

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ABSTRACT

The sliding wear resistance of unidirectional graphite-epoxy fiber composites on an aluminum counterface is investigated quantitatively and by microscopic observation. The fiber orientation and the sliding direction were changed in fixed intervals throughout three dimensional space and, consequently, the wear rates were found to vary by more than three orders of magnitude. In general, the lower rates were obtained when the frictional force was pulling rather than pushing on the fibers and the most severe wear occurred in samples where this force acted in a sideways direction. Different wear processes are identified and discussed. A concise representation of the effect of all possible fiber orientations and sliding directions on the wear rate is proposed and presented. This consists of a contour map of wear rate on a polar stereographic projection.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous investigations have been undertaken to qualify and quantify the behavior of graphite-epoxy composites under the conditions of sliding wear. However, due to the variation in testing parameters and configurations utilized in these studies, the results obtained do not totally coalesce into a coherent and generalized understanding of the effect of fiber orientation on the wear behavior of these materials.

The units in which wear rates are reported by different workers are often not consistent and can be quite misleading. In different reports, the wear rates are given in $\text{cm}^3/\text{cm}\cdot\text{kg}$ for contact

pressures which varied significantly. Only if the rate of material removal changed linearly with the contact pressure can one compare the wear rates reported by the different authors; while this relationship may be true [1] for a monolithic, isotropic material, it has never been established for fiber composites. In addition, most results in the literature report the wear rate in terms of the sliding distance alone even when the sliding speed is changed [2]. It is reasonable to expect that increasing either the contact pressure or sliding speed or both can result in a substantial increase in temperature at the interface. Some resins, common as matrix materials, can begin to degrade at temperatures as low as 180°F which can conceivably be reached under the conditions reported in some investigations [3].

Giltrow and Lancaster [4] studied the wear behavior of graphite-epoxy composites against numerous counterface materials. They conclude, however, that orientation of fibers had little effect on the wear rate. One of the highest wear rates was obtained with an aluminum alloy counterface, a fact that led to the choice of a similar alloy as counterface in this study. Tsukizoe and Ohmae [2] reported for carbon reinforced plastics that for composites in which fibers lie in the wear plane the wear rate was highest when the sliding direction was perpendicular to the fiber and lower when it was parallel. Lancaster [5] on the other hand reports exactly the opposite trend. He also reports an even lower rate when the fibers are perpendicular to the wear plane. Giltrow [6] states that fiber orientation affects the rate significantly only when the fiber content is low. Chang [3] reported the highest rate to occur at 30° to the fibers. Sung & Suh [7] made the most comprehensive study to date on the effect of orientation and their findings agree with those of Tsukizoe and Ohmae [2]. They explained the behavior in terms of fiber-matrix debonding.

In view of the conflicting results reported by different authors, it was decided to conduct a systematic investigation of the orientation effects on wear behavior of composites. This paper describes the experimental work undertaken to characterize the wear behavior of unidirectional fiber composites of low modulus, high strength graphite fibers in an epoxy matrix for any fiber orientation with respect to the wear plane and sliding direction using an aluminum alloy as a counterface.

MATERIALS

The wear samples used in this study were graphite-epoxy fiber reinforced composites containing 60 volume percent of 6 micron diameter low modulus, high strength graphite (type T2C150) in an epoxy resin (HX507 resin system) supplied by Hexcel Corporation of Lancaster, Ohio. The material was supplied as preimpregnated 12" wide tape which was kept below 0°F to prevent resin curing. Individual ply coupons measuring 2.54 cm x 11.4 cm were cut from the tape and stacked until a laminated coupon consisting of seventy plies and measuring approximately 1.3 cm thick was produced. In this manner, four unidirectional samples were made in which the fibers made angles of 0°, 15°, 30°, and 45° with the long axis of the coupon. These samples were cured in a steel mold on a heated platen press at 250°F under a pressure of 4 kg/cm² for two hours, after which the heat was turned off and the mold allowed to cool to room temperature while still under pressure.

The cured samples produced measured approximately 1.2 cm thick, indicating minimal bleeding of the resin. Each coupon was then sectioned on a water-cooled diamond cut-off saw to obtain the test specimens. These nearly cubical specimens measured 1.2 cm x 1.2 cm x 0.95 cm and were cut so that the 1.2 cm square surface to be worn was not an exterior surface on the original coupon and hence would not be affected by possible edge defects. Using this scheme, wear samples were produced in which the fibers made angles of 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75°, and 90° with the wear surface.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The wear testing apparatus utilized in this investigation was somewhat similar to those employed in the pin-on-disc method which has been used in previous studies by numerous workers [4-7]. However, instead of a pin which is usually conical or wedge shaped, a flat surface measuring 1.2 cm x 1.2 cm was pressed against the flat circular surface of a rotating disc 10 cm in diameter. In this manner the contact pressure remained constant throughout the duration of the test rather than decreasing as in some studies.

The disc, or counterface, was made of type 2024-T351 aluminum alloy. This choice of material was made essentially because of the relatively high wear rates obtained by other investigators [4,6] which made it possible to obtain measurable weight losses at low sliding speeds in a reasonable period of time. Before each wear test, the counterface surface was ground with 600 grit silicon carbide paper and, after each test, the counterfaces were resurfaced to remove the wear damage before regrinding.

For each test, a composite sample was placed in a specially designed sample holder which allowed the sample to be oriented such that the plane that is perpendicular to the wear surface and contains the fibers makes a desired angle with the sliding direction. The angles covered by this investigation were 0° , 30° , 60° , 90° , 120° , 150° , and 180° for each angle the fibers made with the wear surface, namely 0° , 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° , and 90° , a total of forty different angle combinations. A static load was applied to the top of the sample holder transmitting a contact pressure of 1.4 kg/cm^2 . The samples were held at a distance of 4 cm from the center of the rotating counterface disc. The resultant sliding speed was 0.3 m/s, too low for significant heat generation during the tests. Figure 1 is a sketch of the testing machine.

To ensure intimate contact between the wear surface of the samples and the counterface, each new sample was worn in situ against the flat surface of a 10 cm disc (Mager Scientific C0-042 silicon carbide abrasive cut-off wheel) placed as a counterface. The abrasive action of the disc levelled and "trued" the wear surface of the sample quickly. The wear

Figure 1. Sketch of the wear apparatus.

surface was then finely ground with 600 grit silicon carbide paper without removing the sample from its supporting mechanism. The aluminum counterface, which was also finished with 600 grit paper, was then installed and the machine run for a break-in period. The purpose of this period was to assure uniform wear on the entire surface. The break-in stage was very different in length from one sample to another, presumably due to differences in fiber orientation, and the wear distance in this stage ranged from 0.1 to 5 kilometers (corresponding to approximately 500 to 20,000 counterface revolutions). The debris of wear from the samples and counterfaces was continually removed by suction and collected so as not to affect the wear process. Once a condition of uniform wear had been achieved, weight loss measurements were made after specified sliding distances. These measurements were made on an analytical balance which was readable to the nearest 0.00001 gram. The wear rate in this work is expressed as the loss in sample height (calculated from weight loss, density, and contact area) per unit sliding distance. Expressed in this manner, the wear rate is a dimensionless quantity. The worn samples were examined by optical as well as scanning electron microscopy and so was the collected wear debris in an effort to establish the wear mechanisms.

RESULTS

In order to represent the results of this investigation, two parameters had to be defined which describe the orientation of the fibers with respect to both the counterface and the sliding direction. These are the two angles θ and ϕ ; the first is the angle the fibers make with the counterface, and the second the angle that the projection of fibers on the wear plane makes with the sliding direction.

The wear rates encountered in this study ranged from less than 1×10^{-10} to more than 1000×10^{-10} . However, it was found that the wear rate is influenced far more by the sliding angle ϕ . Hence, for each set of samples of the same angle θ , the wear rate is plotted as a function of the sliding angle ϕ . These results are presented in Figure 2. It can be seen that for samples with θ of 30° or greater the wear rate drastically increases when ϕ reaches 90° and beyond. In addition to the extremely high wear rates observed in these samples, the scatter was so large that it was decided to show only the trend.

Figure 2. Wear rates as a function of sliding angle ϕ for sets of samples of six fiber angles θ .

A method for representing the wear data obtained for all different orientations completely and concisely has been developed. In this method a polar stereographic projection is made in which the center of the projection represents the normal to the wear plane and a point on the circumference directly above the center represents the sliding direction (motion of fibers relative to the counterface). A point on this projection specifies, by its coordinates θ and ϕ , a particular orientation of fiber relative to the wear plane and the angle between the fiber projection on this plane and the sliding direction. On this projection the values of the wear rates are recorded and contour lines are drawn. The resulting contour map is shown in Figure 3.

DISCUSSION

Upon examination of the wear surfaces produced in this investigation, it is possible to identify several wear processes. In all of these processes the first step seems to be the removal of the matrix to a certain depth (see Figure 4) which depends on the orientation of the fibers. In samples where the fibers are parallel to the counterface, the matrix is first worn to a depth on the order of a fiber diameter. Then, if the sliding direction is parallel to the fibers, the frictional force pulls, or drags, on the fibers in the longitudinal direction and causes transverse cracking (see Figure 5) which leads to removal of portions of the fiber starting at its trailing end. If, however, the sliding direction is perpendicular to the fibers, the imposed frictional force bends the fibers and causes transverse cracks, leading again to material removal of any fragment of the bent fiber (see Figure 6). It is obvious that it is far easier to crack a rod-shaped object such as a fiber by bending than by direct pull. Hence, one would expect the wear normal to the fiber direction to be more severe than along the fiber. Sliding in directions between these two limiting orientations results in a combination of these two modes of material removal. Thus, the tendency for cracking and material removal should increase as the sliding angle ϕ increases all the way from 0° to 90° which is indeed the case. In samples where the fibers do not lie in the wear plane the matrix wear continues until the fibers shield it from further wear and the frictional force is carried entirely by the fibers. The depth of matrix wear when this

Figure 3. Contour map of dimensionless wear rates expressed in units of 10^{-10} on a polar stereographic projection simultaneously depicting the effects of fiber orientation θ and sliding direction ϕ .

happens is small for samples where the fibers make a small angle with the wear plane, and in the case where the fibers are nearly perpendicular to this plane the depth of wear of the matrix can be quite large.

The general tendency for all fiber inclinations is that the least wear occurs when ϕ is much smaller than 90° ; much greater wear is encountered when ϕ is substantially greater than 90° , and by far the highest wear rate of all is observed when ϕ is in the vicinity of 90° . One may reason that when ϕ is much smaller than 90° the frictional force

Figure 4. An oblique SEM view of lightly worn surface showing the preferential matrix removal.

Figure 5. Optical micrograph of surface of sample worn along the fiber axis, showing transverse cracking. (1000X)

exerts a pull or drag on the fibers; when it is much greater than 90° the slender fibers are pushed upon and tend to buckle, and when ϕ is in the vicinity of 90° this sideways force bends the fibers. Of course, breaking a fiber by either buckling or bending is far easier than breaking one by direct pull.

When θ is small and the sliding direction angle ϕ is relatively small, the frictional force pulls on the fiber and causes them to crack near the trailing edge of its elliptical wear surface. These cracks are

Figure 6. Optical micrograph of sample surface containing fibers worn in a transverse direction, showing fiber bending and cracking. (400X)

more or less perpendicular to the sliding direction, as Figures 7 and 8 illustrate, and the crack surface is perpendicular to the wear plane as has been determined by examination of the debris. Eventually, a wedge-shaped portion of the fiber at the trailing end is separated. This is facilitated by the lack of a strong fiber to matrix bond, suggested by the fact that all fiber segments observed in the wear debris had clean surfaces with no adhering matrix material (see Figure 9). This process continues with cracks forming closer and closer to the leading edge of the fiber until the fiber can no longer shield the matrix from further wear and the entire process is repeated. However, once the original flat surface has been worn away, it is difficult to follow the process by direct observation. As the sliding angle θ approaches 90° , the cracks have further to propagate and the broken parts are longer, accounting for the increased wear rates. When $\phi \geq 90^\circ$ and θ is not very small (i.e. above 15°) the wear process is dominated by bending and/or buckling of the fibers. Together with debonding, this results in the removal of relatively long, intact segments of fiber (with length to diameter ratio of approximately 3) and allows further wear of the composite. At sliding directions close to 180° , the presentation geometry of the fibers to the counterface is analogous to that of a cutting tool applied to a workpiece. This analogy is substantiated by the generation of spiral turnings of the counterface material at the leading edge of the sample (see Figure 10).

Figure 7. Optical micrograph of the worn surface of sample with 15° fiber angle and 0° sliding direction, showing cracking and fiber fragment removal. (1000X)

Figure 8. SEM photograph of the worn surface of sample with 60° fiber angle and 30° sliding direction, showing separation and removal of wedge-shaped fiber fragments.

Figure 9. SEM view of wear debris collected from sample with fiber angle 45° and sliding direction 180°, showing long fiber segments. (1000X)

Figure 10. SEM photograph of a chip ploughed out of the counterface and found in the debris of Figure 9. (1500X)

CONCLUSIONS

1. Under the experimental conditions of this investigation, the wear rate and wear mechanism are strongly influenced by both fiber orientation and sliding direction.
2. The least wear occurs when the fibers make an angle of 45° with the wear plane and the sliding direction is along the fiber projection with $\phi = 0^\circ$ (dragging mode).
3. The wear rate is extremely high when the fibers make 30° or more with the wear plane and the sliding direction is at $\phi = 90^\circ$ to 180° (bending to ploughing mode).
4. An informative and concise method of describing the effect of orientation on wear rate is mapping contour lines on a polar stereographic projection.

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